

Couples' Reproductive Decisions: An Inter-Spousal Communication Amongst Young Couples of Bihar

Paper Id : 18528 Submission Date : 02/02/2024 Acceptance Date : 18/02/2024 Publication Date : 23/02/2024

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10821754

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Abstract

The crucial reproductive decisions being taken by a couple are such a complex phenomena that it becomes really difficult to capture the decision making process and to determine whether one spouse is dominating over others or the decision is jointly taken after proper communication and negotiation. There are multiple factors such as educational background, socio-economic condition, female literacy, female occupation, type of families etc. contributes and affects in reproductive decisions like contraceptive uses, delaying first child and spacing between first and second child. The prime respondents for this study were newly married couple / married couple with 0 child and married couple with one child . Among married women with 0 child 83.5 % respondents said that they take FP/RH related decisions jointly with their husbands. Only 11.5 % respondents said that such decisions are taken by their spouse. When the same question was asked from married men with 0 child only 39 % respondents said that they jointly take decisions with their wife on the issue of FP /RH. This percentage was nearly half of the responses given by their wives. Almost 42.5 male respondents (married men with 0 child) said that they alone take decisions on the matter of RH/FP. There was a certain gap observed between husbands and wives of 0 child while communicating and taking crucial RH/FP decision. Among married women with 1 child 57 % respondents said that they jointly take FP/RH related decisions but at the same time 31 % respondents said that such decisions were taken by their husbands. Among married men with 1 child 49 % respondents said that they jointly take crucial RH/FDP decision with their wife but 39.5 % respondents said that they alone take RH/FP related decisions. This study concluded that men role was extremely significant while taking crucial/ most influential RH/FP related decisions. Most of the RH/FP related decisions are taken either by the husband or jointly with wives. Another finding of the study was that the couple were hardly have any impact of influencers/family members on RH/FP related matters.

Keywords Reproductive Health (RH), Couple, Decisions, Influencers, Family Planning (FP).

Introduction

An Inter-spousal communication is a complex dimension between husband and wife while taking up crucial family planning and reproductive decisions. In India, population and development programmes, and medical institutions often neglect the male's influence on decisions related to reproductive health (RH) issues, as well as male behaviour and sexual health needs. Today, policy makers are trying to get more and more men involved in RH programs. There are certain barriers, however, such as social and cultural obstacles, weak commitment by policy makers or inadequate policy, insufficient and inappropriate information. Interventions to involve males in RH programs are intended, for instance, to ensure more responsible sexual behaviour, to increase contraceptive methods used, and to strengthen information sharing between husbands and wives.

Communication between husband and wife enabled them to know each other's attitudes toward family planning and use of contraceptives. It allows them to voice their concerns about reproductive health issues, such as worries about unwanted pregnancies or sexually transmitted diseases (STDs). Couple communication also encourages shared decision-making and an equal role for both sexes. Research over more than 40 years consistently demonstrated that men and women who discuss family planning are more likely to use contraceptives, to use them more effectively and to have fewer children. In contrast, when

men and women did not know their partners' fertility desires and attitudes toward family planning or contraceptive preferences, there could be unintended pregnancies, leading perhaps to unsafe abortions, and a risk of transmission of STDs. In societies where the male is the decision-maker in the family, he makes important decisions such as those relating to having or not having a child, using or not using contraceptives.

Purpose Of The Study

Despite rapid economic and social development in recent decades, India retained the large populations of extreme poverty and virtual isolation from national progress. The state of Bihar is arguably one of the least developed and most populous of India's 28 states, with 84 percent of the population living in rural areas (much of which is flooded for several months a year). Eighty percent of the population belongs to the lower castes, which helps to hold the poorest citizens in poverty. Women and girls face extreme economic and social inequality and are usually married young and pressed by parents, in-laws and the wider community to prove their fertility by having a child immediately. Girls are brought up to be obedient to parents, husbands and mothers-in-law, and only 46.3 percent of women interviewed usually participated in household decisions.

Government of India family planning programs had historically focused on women who already had two or three children, persuading them to adopt permanent or long-term methods. Little attention was paid to educating adolescents and young married couples on "planning" the timing and spacing of children according to their economic and health needs. Traditional reproductive health programs had not targeted youth, given barriers posed by cultural norms favouring early marriage and proof of fertility.

The prime purpose of the study is to see the role and influence of husbands and wives in taking crucial reproductive decisions such as contraceptive use and how the couple arrive at the decision. Whether the decisions are taken independently by the respondents or influenced by the spouse or jointly taken by the couple. The specialty of the study is to compare the crucial reproductive decisions in the context of husband and wife and understanding the dynamics of spousal communication.

Aim of study

The prime objectives of the study are as follows;

1. To find out the inter-spousal communication between the husband and the wife for Reproductive / Family Planning decisions.
2. To explore the impact of background variables in taking crucial reproductive decisions.

Review of Literature

Except for a few studies, the literature on Indian researches pertaining to husband-wife communication and family planning is scanty. Nevertheless, two important studies are noteworthy. The study of Rama kumar and Gopal revealed that along the socioeconomic scale, couples in a higher position communicated more with each other than others. They concluded with the hope that it should be possible to demonstrate that communication between husband and wife on matters relating to family planning was a factor that influenced fertility. Later, in 1975, Mukherjee brought out the importance of husband-wife communication on family planning matters and suggested certain policy modifications to the family planning programme and mass media coverage in order to improve family planning acceptance. In a recent study conducted by Pradhan, M.R. & Mondal, S. in 2023 concluded that living arrangement of a woman had a significant association with contraceptive use in South Asia. Modern limiting methods were significantly higher among women living with MIL in India. The study reflected that MIL also plays an important role while it comes to RH/FP related decisions taken by the couple.

Methodology

The primary and secondary methods were used for the data collection. Under the primary method, a face to face interview was conducted separately for husband and wife. A semi-structured interview-schedule was developed to conduct interviews.

The secondary sources such as published reports, studies etc. were used to substantiate the findings of the study.

Sampling

This research study covered 200 couples of the age-group of 15-24 years and having no child/0 child and 200 couples of the age-group 15-24 having one living child. The interview was conducted during June - September, 2010 separately for the husbands and for the wives so that nobody can influence each other while expressing their feelings or views during interview. The multi-stage random sampling method was used to select the samples where couple was considered as sampling unit.

For selecting the couples the following mechanism was adopted –

Bihar was divided among 9 Divisions.

Firstly, Out of 9 divisions two divisions were randomly selected. These selected divisions are Patna and Magadh.

Secondly, Out of the selected divisions, two districts were randomly selected. These districts were Nalanda (Patna Division) and Gaya (Magadh Division).

Thirdly, Out of the selected two districts, two blocks were randomly selected. These blocks were Islampur (Nalanda) and Giriak (Gaya).

Fourthly, Out of each selected block 100 couples of the age-group 15-24 having no child and 100 couples of the age-group 15-24 having one child were randomly selected for the interview.

Therefore, 100 sample respondents having no child & 100 sample respondents having one child were interviewed from each division. The total number of 400 couples sample respondents were interviewed for this study. So, individually 800 sample respondents were interviewed for this study.

Analysis

The collected data was entered in MS Excel sheet and analyzed by using Statistical Packages in Social Sciences (SPSS). The bi-variate analysis was done for elaborate understanding of the subjects of the study.

Findings

A. Background of the Respondents

Before analyzing the data and concluding the findings, it was very important to know about the basic characteristics of the respondents. Here basic characteristics means all the independent variables selected for analyzing the data and for measuring the findings keeping independent variables as base. The prime independent variables selected in this study were; Education, Caste, etc. Some of the independent variables were excluded from the further analysis of data as there were not sufficient numbers of responses obtained.

The background features of respondents provided complete background related information of the respondents. This would help in understanding the profile of the respondents and interpretation of data. The background related information is presented from Table 1.

Table-1: Name of District & Respondent Type

District	Respondent Type				Total
	Married Women 0 Child	Married Men 0 Child	Married Women 1 Child	Married Men 1 Child	
Nalanda	100	100	100	100	400
	25.0%	25.0%	25.0%	25.0%	100.0%
Gaya	100	100	100	100	400
	25.0%	25.0%	25.0%	25.0%	100.0%
Total	200	200	200	200	800
	25.0%	25.0%	25.0%	25.0%	100.0%

Source : Primary data (Ph.D. Thesis)

In this research study total 400 couples were interviewed. 200 couples were interviewed from Nalanda district and remaining 200 couples were interviewed from Gaya district. Out of 200 couples 100 couples were interviewed from those who were not having any living child at the

time of interview and 100 couples were having one living child with them. The purpose of taking two types of couples for interview was to understand the dynamics of reproductive decisions at different stages. Initially, it was tried to conduct interview jointly (husband & wife together) but it was difficult as the husband was dominating over their wife during the interview. Therefore, husband and wife was interviewed separately to minimize the influence and to ensure the objectivity of the research.

In a nutshell, total 800 interviews were conducted in which 400 interviews were held for husbands & 400 interviews held for wives. An attempt was to ask similar questions from the husbands & the wives to find the similarities and differences of opinion among the husbands & wives. It was really difficult to compare the responses of each husband and wife, therefore collective comparison was done to conclude the decision making aspects in this study.

Significant Findings

The key findings of the study revealed the details of inter-spousal communication and how they do generally arrived the various reproductive / family planning decisions. **Table 2** tried to explain and understand the most influential person while taking the crucial FP / Reproductive health related decisions. This answers the query of the most important persons who not only participated while taking crucial reproductive decisions but also helped in understanding the most influencing person. The response categories were respondents, spouse, jointly with spouse, Mother in law, Father in law etc.

The purpose of keeping these options were to make sure the most important players in taking reproductive decisions. We all know that these were crucial persons who influence the couples while taking reproductive decisions. The data were analyzed and presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Respondent Type & Most Influential in Taking FP Decision

Most Influencing in taking reproductive decisions	Respondent Type				Total
	Married Women 0 Child	Married Women 1 Child	Married Men 0 Child	Married Men 1 Child	
Respondent	1	5	85	78	169
	.5%	2.5%	42.5%	39.0%	21.1%
Spouse	23	62	6	13	104
	11.5%	31.0%	3.0%	6.5%	13.0%
Jointly Husband & Wife	167	114	78	98	457
	83.5%	57.0%	39.0%	49.0%	57.1%
Mother in Law	6	16	10	3	35
	3.0%	8.0%	5.0%	1.5%	4.4%
Father in Law	0	0	20	8	28
	.0%	.0%	10.0%	4.0%	3.5%

Grandfather / Mother (In Laws)	0	0	1	0	1
	.0%	.0%	.5%	.0%	.1%
Respondent along with Spouse & Parents	2	3	0	0	5
	1.0%	1.5%	.0%	.0%	.6%
Other relatives	1	0	0	0	1
	.5%	.0%	.0%	.0%	.1%
Total	200	200	200	200	800
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source : Primary data (Ph.D. Thesis)

Among married women with 0 child 83.5 % respondents said that they take FP/RH related decisions jointly with their husbands. Only 11.5 % respondents said that such decisions were taken by their spouse. When the same question was asked from married men with 0 child only 39 % respondents said that they jointly with their wife take decisions on the issue of FP /RH. This percentage was nearly half of the responses given by their wives. Almost 42.5 male respondents (married men with 0 child) said that they alone take decisions on the matter of RH/FP. So, there was a certain gap observed between husbands and wives of 0 child while taking crucial RH/FP decision.

Among married women with 1 child 57 % respondents said that they jointly take FP/RH related decisions with their husbands but at the same time 31 % respondents said that such decisions were taken by their husbands. Among married men with 1 child 49 % respondents said that they jointly with wife take crucial RH/FP decision but 39.5 respondents said that they alone take RH/FP related decisions. Again, the differences between husbands and wives were observed amongst the couple having 1 child.

Out of total responses of 800 respondents, 57 % said that they jointly take decisions on RH/FP related issues with their spouse. Almost 21 % respondents said that they alone take RH/FP related decisions in the family and almost all the respondents who had given such response are male.

To conclude , it can be said that men play crucial role while taking crucial/ most influential RH/FP related decisions. Most of the RH/FP related decisions were taken either by husbands or jointly with wives. The interference or influencers by other family members on RH/FP related matters were found to be negligible.

It was tried to find out whether the caste play any role in taking crucial family planning decision. The analysed data presented in **Table - 3** . Among married women with 0 child, 72.0 % SC women said that they take crucial reproductive decision jointly with their husband whereas 87.0 % said that they take crucial reproductive health decision jointly with their husband and 100.0 % General women said the same response. Based on the data, it can be interpreted that Caste also played an important role in discussing family planning issues and taking crucial family planning decision. Such inter-spousal communication was found highest amongst general caste couple (100 %), amongst OBC Couples (87 %) and amongst SC couples (72 %).

Table 3: Respondent Type , Caste & Final Family Planning Decision

Respondent Type	Caste	Final Family Planning Decision							Total	
		Respondent	Spouse	Jointly Husband & Wife	Mother in Law	Father in Law	Grand father / Mother (In Laws)	Respondent along with Spouse & Parents		Other relatives
Married Women 0 Child	SC	1	9	38	3			2	0	53
		1.9%	17.0%	71.7%	5.7%			3.8%	.0%	100.0%
	OBC	0	14	121	3			0	1	139
		.0%	10.1%	87.1%	2.2%			.0%	.7%	100.0%
	General	0	0	8	0			0	0	8
		.0%	.0%	100.0%	.0%			.0%	.0%	100.0%
Total	1	23	167	6			2	1	200	
	.5%	11.5%	83.5%	3.0%			1.0%	.5%	100.0%	
Married Women 1 Child	SC	1	14	27	5			0		47
		2.1%	29.8%	57.4%	10.6%			.0%		100.0%
	OBC	4	46	86	11			3		150
		2.7%	30.7%	57.3%	7.3%			2.0%		100.0%
	General	0	2	1	0			0		3
		.0%	66.7%	33.3%	.0%			.0%		100.0%
Total	5	62	114	16			3		200	
	2.5%	31.0%	57.0%	8.0%			1.5%		100.0%	
Married Men 0 Child	SC	17	0	16	2	6	0			41
		41.5%	.0%	39.0%	4.9%	14.6%	.0%			100.0%
	OBC	67	6	62	8	14	1			158
		42.4%	3.8%	39.2%	5.1%	8.9%	.6%			100.0%
	General	1	0	0	0	0	0			1
		100.0%	.0%	.0%	.0%	.0%	.0%			100.0%
Total	85	6	78	10	20	1			200	
	42.5%	3.0%	39.0%	5.0%	10.0%	.5%			100.0%	
Married Men 1 Child	SC	13	1	19	2	4				39
		33.3%	2.6%	48.7%	5.1%	10.3%				100.0%
	OBC	65	10	76	1	4				156
		41.7%	6.4%	48.7%	.6%	2.6%				100.0%
	General	0	2	3	0	0				5
		.0%	40.0%	60.0%	.0%	.0%				100.0%
Total	78	13	98	3	8				200	
	39.0%	6.5%	49.0%	1.5%	4.0%				100.0%	

Source: Primary data (Ph.D. Thesis)

Among married men with 0 child the same question was asked from the respondents of each category and the response was surprising. Only 39.0 % respondents of all categories said that they take crucial family planning related decision jointly with their wives. The responses given by SC male and OBC male respondents followed the similar pattern and not much differences were observed between their responses. As there was only one respondent from General category, his opinion could not be taken into consideration for analysis and comparison purpose.

Among married women with 1 child, almost 57.0 % respondents of all categories said that they jointly with their husband take crucial family planning decision. Therefore, caste does not influence in taking crucial family planning decision. The similar responses were observed with the respondents of married men with 1 child. Almost 49.0 % respondents of SC & OBC category said that they jointly with their wife take crucial family planning decision.

So, in a nutshell, it can be concluded that caste did not have much influence among the respondents of each category while taking crucial family planning decision. But, the data clearly exhibits that there was a huge difference in the responses of male & female categories when it comes to take crucial family planning decisions. And the male responses indicated that still man dominate over his wife in taking crucial family planning decision.

The next **Table -4** tried to find out whether education played any role in taking crucial family planning decisions on men & women respondents or not.

Table 4: Respondent Type , Education & Final Family Planning Decision

Respondent Type	Education	Final Family Planning Decision								Total
		Respondent	Spouse	Jointly Husband & Wife	Mother in Law	Father in Law	Grand father / Mother (In Laws)	Respondent along with Spouse & Parents	Other relatives	
Married Women 0 Child	Yes	0	16	78	2			0	1	97
		.0%	16.5%	80.4%	2.1%			.0%	1.0%	100.0%
	No	1	7	89	4			2	0	103
		1.0%	6.8%	86.4%	3.9%			1.9%	.0%	100.0%
Total		1	23	167	6			2	1	200
		.5%	11.5%	83.5%	3.0%			1.0%	.5%	100.0%
Married Women 1 Child	Yes	2	32	47	6			1		88
		2.3%	36.4%	53.4%	6.8%			1.1%		100.0%
	No	3	30	67	10			2		112
		2.7%	26.8%	59.8%	8.9%			1.8%		100.0%
Total		5	62	114	16			3		200
		2.5%	31.0%	57.0%	8.0%			1.5%		100.0%
Married Men 0 Child	Yes	56	4	54	7	15	1			137
		40.9%	2.9%	39.4%	5.1%	10.9%	.7%			100.0%
	No	29	2	24	3	5	0			63
		46.0%	3.2%	38.1%	4.8%	7.9%	.0%			100.0%
Total		85	6	78	10	20	1			200
		42.5%	3.0%	39.0%	5.0%	10.0%	.5%			100.0%
Married Men 1 Child	Yes	57	11	74	1	7				150
		38.0%	7.3%	49.3%	.7%	4.7%				100.0%
	No	21	2	24	2	1				50
		42.0%	4.0%	48.0%	4.0%	2.0%				100.0%
Total		78	13	98	3	8				200
		39.0%	6.5%	49.0%	1.5%	4.0%				100.0%

Among married women with 0 child, almost 80.4% educated respondents and 86.4 % uneducated respondent said that they jointly with their husbands take crucial family planning decision. It means even the educated women takes consent of their husband while taking family planning decision.

Among married men with 0 child, only 39.0% educated respondents and 38.1 % uneducated respondents said that they take crucial family planning decision jointly with their wives. Therefore, the education did not have much influences on the educated and uneducated male when it comes to take crucial family planning decision. Only 39.0 % men respondents said that they discussed with their wives before taking family planning decisions and rests of the respondents said that they alone take crucial family planning decision.

Among married women with 1 child, almost 53.4 % educated women respondents & 59.8 % uneducated respondents said that they take crucial family planning decision jointly with their husbands. And 36.4 % educated respondents and 26.8 % uneducated respondents said that the crucial family planning decision had been taken by their husbands. It means the current education system did not provide sufficient empowerment to the women so that they could discuss crucial family planning issues with their husbands.

Almost 49.0 % educated & uneducated married men with 1 child respondents said that they generally take crucial family planning decision jointly with their wives. But again almost 50.0 % educated & uneducated respondents said that they alone take family planning decision. So, the education did not have significant impact on the men respondents to sensitize them to at least discuss with their counterparts before taking any family planning decision.

Conclusion

In this research study , the parents contribution in influencing the couples while taking FP decision was found to be very less. It means couples taking crucial reproductive decisions in their life. They were not much influenced by their parents / guardians.

Among married women with 0 child 83.5 % respondents said that they take FP/RH related decisions jointly with their husbands. Only 11.5 % respondents said that such decisions were taken by their spouse. When the same question was asked from married men with 0 child only 39 % respondents said that they jointly with their wife take decisions on the issue of FP /RH. This percentage is nearly half of the responses given by their wives. Almost 42.5 male respondents (married men with 0 child) said that they alone take decisions on the matter of

RH/FP. So, the study revealed the evident inter-spousal communication gaps between husbands and wives of couples having 0 child especially on taking crucial RH/FP decision.

Among married women with 1 child 57 % respondents said that they jointly take FP/RH related decisions but at the same time 31 % respondents said that such decisions are taken by their husbands. Among married men with 1 child 49 % respondents said that they jointly with wife take crucial RH/FDP decision but 39.5 % respondents said that they alone take RH/FP related decisions. The study revealed that since the duration of togetherness increases, the inter-spousal communication smoothen on RH/FP issues with respect to the couples with 0 child and it was evident from the responses given by male respondents with 0 and 1 child.

Therefore, it can be concluded that men play crucial role while taking crucial/ most influential RH/FP related decisions. Most of the RH/FP related decisions were taken either by husbands or jointly with wives. The interference or influence by the other family members on RH/FP related matters are negligible.

Among married men with 0 child, only 39.0% educated respondents and 38.1 % uneducated respondents said that they take crucial family planning decision jointly with their wives. Therefore, the education did not have much influence on the educated and uneducated male when it comes to take crucial family planning decision. Similarly, caste / category did not have much influences over taking RH/FP decisions amongst couple with 0 and 1child.

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